

Research Article

Examination of the Türk Müziği (Turkish Music) journal, a folkloric bridge for Turkish-speaking states

Hasan Said Tortop¹

Formerly affiliated with Ufuk University, Ankara, Türkiye

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Abstract

Türk Müziği (Turkish Music) journal, as a scientific and academic journal, began its publication life in 2021. It appears to serve as a platform that enhances the visibility of the works of Turkish music researchers. This study aims to examine the Türk Müziği journal from a technical perspective based on certain criteria. The document analysis method, one of the qualitative research methods, was used in the research. The results of the research indicate that the journal's purpose and scope statements are clearly written. It is observed that the aim of Türk Müziği is stated as "to be a common academic platform for music research in Turkish-speaking states." The journal includes sections on ethical principles and publication policies, as well as peer review policies. The journal is published four times a year and the publication language is specified as Turkish only. Türk Müziği has published 9 issues and 66 articles so far. Of the published articles, 22 were prepared by authors from Azerbaijan and 44 by authors from Türkiye. In this regard, it is seen that Türk Müziği has not yet published articles from other Turkish-speaking states. It is also observed that the editorial board members are only from Azerbaijan and Turkey. When analyzing the keywords of the articles published in TM, it is found that out of 272 keywords, Music (10), Turkish Music (4), Genre (3), Azerbaijan (3), and Folk Song (3) are repeated. Twenty-five keywords are repeated twice, and the other keywords are repeated once. Türk Müziği organizes training to improve article writing skills under the formation of Turkish Music Academy on its website. Additionally, it provides support services to young scientists in the field of music. Türk Müziği plans to publish a special issue on Turkish Music Philosophy. In this study, the technical examination of the TM journal was conducted. It is recommended that future research includes quality evaluation based on certain criteria.

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Introduction

Türkiye provides higher education in music through various institutions such as conservatories, faculties that train music educators, and research institutes. These institutions play a crucial role in enriching the nation's musical culture and cultivating professional musicians. Conservatories in Türkiye are among the most established institutions. These conservatories are dedicated to training artists who specialize in both Western and Turkish music. Initially founded in Istanbul and Ankara, these conservatories offer advanced education encompassing both theoretical knowledge and performance at a high level. Currently, there are approximately forty conservatories across the country (Çolakoğlu, 2010). In addition, the music education departments within faculties of education serve as institutions responsible for training future music teachers, ensuring their development through pedagogical formation (Yıldırım, 2018). Institutes

¹ Asst.Prof.Dr., Formerly affiliated with Ufuk University, Ankara, Türkiye Email: hasansaidfen@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-0899-4033

of Fine Arts and Social Sciences are also instrumental in the education of academics and researchers in the field of music, offering master's and doctoral programs. For example, Istanbul Technical University is a notable institution in the realm of Turkish music studies (Aksoy, 2015). The role of these institutes in cultivating researchers within the music discipline is particularly significant.

In recent years, academic interest in music research in Türkiye has grown considerably. This increase is reflected in the rising number of academic journals dedicated to the field of music. Academic journals serve not only as vehicles for the production and dissemination of scientific knowledge but also as essential tools for enhancing the visibility and recognition of this knowledge within both national and international academic communities (Tortop & Demirel, 2023). The status of academic journals in the field of music in Türkiye requires both quantitative and qualitative evaluation. This examination aims to provide an overview of the current state of these academic journals in Türkiye and to identify the challenges they encounter.

The Status of Academic Journals in the Field of Music in Türkiye

Recently, there has been a noticeable increase in the number of academic journals published in the field of music in Türkiye. This growth parallels the rise in the number of research institutes offering graduate-level education. The increase in the number of master's and doctoral students, along with their need to publish their research, has driven the demand for more academic journals in this field. Additionally, initiatives like the Dergipark project, developed by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK), have supported academic publishing in Türkiye (Dergipark, 2023). Dergipark has facilitated the broader dissemination of Türkiye's academic journals and helped them conform to international standards. However, a significant portion of these journals is still inadequately represented in international indexes. This lack of representation diminishes their visibility in the global academic community and, consequently, reduces the impact factor of the published research.

In their study, Demirel and Tortop (2023) focused on examining the quality of academic journals in the field of music in Türkiye. The journals they analyzed include *Rast Musicology Journal*, *Turkish Music Journal*, *Musicologist*, *Online Journal of Music Sciences*, *Ethnomusicology Journal*, and *AKU Journal of Academic Music Research*, totaling six journals. This number is quite insufficient. Furthermore, when these journals were examined qualitatively, it was found that academic music journals in Türkiye face significant challenges, not only in quantity but also in quality. Tortop and Demirel (2023) noted that many academic journals in the field of music have deficiencies in their "aim and scope" statements, which prevents them from clearly defining their identity. For instance, some journals have publication policies that do not align with their titles; a notable example is the *Balkan Music and Arts Journal*, which fails to publish enough articles related to Balkan music.

Another critical issue with academic journals in the field of music is their low representation in international indexes. Among the music journals in Türkiye, only two are indexed in globally recognized databases such as Scopus and Web of Science (Tortop & Demirel, 2023). This situation negatively impacts the international competitiveness of academic publishing in Türkiye. Being indexed in these databases not only enhances the academic prestige of the journals but also ensures that the published articles are read by a broader academic audience and receive more citations.

Moreover, many academic journals in Türkiye encounter difficulties in defining and implementing their publication policies. Yıldızeli (2011) points out that the editors of academic journals in Türkiye face challenges in accurately defining the goals and objectives of their journals, which adversely affects the quality of the journals. Additionally, the volunteer-based editorial system makes it difficult to manage the journals professionally and hinders their long-term development. As a result of their study, Demirel and Tortop (2023) recommended that music journals in Türkiye review their aims and scope sections, improve their publication policies, and increase their rates of international indexing to enhance their quality.

The Quality of Music Articles in Türkiye

Another significant issue is the quality of the articles published in these journals. Improving the quality of articles will indirectly enhance the overall quality of music journals. In this context, Tortop (2023) presented important findings regarding the quality of music article writing in an article that academically evaluates music research in Türkiye. The

study identified seventeen different quality criteria that should be considered when writing music articles, and articles published in *Türk Müziği* and the Journal for the Interdisciplinary Art and Education (JIAE) were examined based on these criteria (Tortop, 2023).

It was found that basic elements such as organization, clarity, and precision were generally not given sufficient importance in the writing of the abstract section in music articles. In the majority of the articles reviewed in the two journals, the abstract was found to be weak in reflecting the overall content of the article and in capturing the reader's interest. Additionally, the introduction section was not structured adequately or compellingly, and there was a lack of a well-defined theoretical foundation. The insufficient development of a theoretical framework in music research is identified as a factor that could negatively impact the scientific validity and reliability of the research (Tortop, 2023).

The literature review was also criticized for its lack of coverage of international research. It was observed that most of the reviewed articles addressed the literature only at a national level and did not provide a sufficiently broad perspective in an international context. This limitation hinders the contribution of the research to universal scientific knowledge and leads to fewer citations in the international arena (Popper, 2015; Tortop, 2023).

Furthermore, deficiencies were observed in the selection of research methods and data analysis. It was particularly noted that advanced statistical analyses were not sufficiently employed in quantitative research and that the methods were not explained in detail. These shortcomings are considered significant factors that diminish the scientific value of the research. Additionally, the absence of discussions on the limitations of the research and the insufficient depth of the findings and conclusions were also highlighted as areas of concern (Kuhn, 2015; Tortop, 2023).

In conclusion, it is emphasized that certain standards need to be developed to improve the quality of article writing in the field of music research in Türkiye. In this regard, the importance of establishing a theoretical framework, addressing literature on an international level, selecting appropriate methods, and providing detailed explanations are highlighted. Enhancing academic quality in music research will lead to the publication of more impactful articles that receive higher citations both nationally and internationally (Tortop, 2023).

Institutionalization of Turkish Music Research

The institutionalization of Turkish music research continues both at the conservatory level, as seen in examples like Istanbul Technical University and Ege University, and through institutes now present in many universities (Çakır, 2019; Özkan, 2017). However, it is also a fact that the academic quality of institutes varies across different regions in Türkiye, depending on the levels of socio-economic development. Currently, six academic journals are serving this field in terms of academic publishing. For the development of qualified personnel such as musicians, music educators, and music researchers, the growth of these institutions is essential. When examining the institutional status of journals related to academic publishing, it is noted that among the six journals studied by Tortop and Demirel (2023), one is privately owned, while the others are associated with associations or state universities.

Research Problem

In this study, the *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) journal, one of the academic journals in the field of music, has been selected for examination due to its unique and specific aims and objectives. The role of this journal as a bridge in music folklore between Turkish-speaking countries is particularly significant. The main research problem of this study is:

- What is the quantitative and qualitative status of the sections that should be present in the *Turkish Music* journal as an academic journal?

Method

In this study, the document analysis method, one of the qualitative research methods, was used. The object of analysis and the document of the study consist of all the information reflected on the website of the *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) journal. In this context, the sections on the website of the relevant academic journal and the academic articles it has published were selected as the documents of this research.

Findings

This section presents an examination of the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the *Turkish Music* journal.

Technical Features of the *Türk Müziği* (Turkish Music) Journal

The website of the *Turkish Music* journal (OJS) includes the following pages: About, Ethical Principles and Publication Policy, Peer Review Policy, TM Authors, Special Issue: Philosophy of Turkish Music, Open Access Policy, Article Retraction and Withdrawal Policy, Complaints and Appeals Policy, Fee Policy, Archiving Policy, Masthead, Submissions, Contact, and Indexing.

The journal is published four times a year, with the publication language specified as Turkish only. The scope of TM includes Turkish Music Theories, Philosophy of Turkish Music, History of Turkish Music, Practices of Turkish Music, Turkish Musical Instruments, Interdisciplinary Research on Turkish Music, Turkish Popular Music, Turkish Classical Music, Turkish Folk Music, Turkish Sufi Music, Music of Turkish-speaking Countries (such as Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan), Turkish Music Education-Pedagogy, Turkish Instrumental Education, and Turkish Instrument Design.

Authors are required to download the article template and format their articles accordingly before submission. The Copyright Transfer Form and Plagiarism Report are requested during the submission of articles. It is observed that a "Masthead" page has been created regarding the technical features of TM.

Aims and Objectives of the *Türk Müziği* (Turkish Music) Journal

Regarding this, it is stated that "The *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) (TM) journal is a scientific, academic, and international journal where interdisciplinary research on Turkish music is conducted. It aims to be the primary source and platform for in-depth analysis of Turkish music. Turkish music, with its rich heritage that has left its mark across many lands throughout history, continues to be a subject of interest for researchers worldwide."

As noted, the objectives of the *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) journal emphasize its role as a platform at the core of Turkish music research. Particularly, the focus on publishing in the Turkish language and accepting articles from all Turkish-speaking countries indicates that *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) aims to serve as a bridge.

Examination of Articles Published in the *Turkish Music* Journal

It is observed that the *Turkish Music* journal has published nine issues and 66 articles so far. The methodological consistency of the articles published in the *Turkish Music* journal is ensured by the article template provided

Makale başlığı: Genç Bilge (Young Wise) dergileri için word şablonu¹

Ad Soyad² ve Ad Soyad³ (sorumlu yazar iğaresi)

Bilim, Önerme, Şehir, Oku (Sadece sorumlu yazar bilgileri)

Öz

Giriş cümlesi, araştırmanın önemi, araştırmanın amaç ve problemi, araştırma modeli, katılımcılar/dokümanlar/özetler, veri toplama araçları, veri analizi, bulgular, sonuç, öneriler (Yaklaşık 300 kelime sınırlı dikkat ediniz)

Anahtar Kelimeler: kelime1, kelime2, kelime3, (kelime baş harflerinin küçük harf olması, en fazla 6 kelime)

Giriş (12 punto)

EB Garamond 11 punto 1.15 satır aralığı

Kuramsal Çerçeve (ikinci düzey başlık)

Literatür Taraması (ikinci düzey başlık)

Araştırmanın Önemi (ikinci düzey başlık)

Makalenin teknik kalitesi (Çalışma, değerlendiril ve beşinci düzey başlıklar için sadece ilk harf büyük)

Araştırmanın Amacı/Problemi (ikinci düzey başlık)

- > Problem 1?
- > Problem 2?
- > Makalenin içinde maddeleri göstermek için bu sembolü kullanıyoruz. Sayı ya da başka madde sembolü kullanmıyoruz.

Yöntem

Araştırma Modeli

Katılımcılar/Dokümanlar/Esaslar

Analiz

Süreç

Bulgular/Bulgular ve Tartışma

Tablo 1. Katılımcıların özellikleri

No	Cinsiyet	Yaş	Kodlar
1	Kadın	24	P1
2	Erkek	22	P2
3	Kadın	21	P3
4	Erkek	22	P4
5	Kadın	22	P5
6	Erkek	23	P6

Figure 1. Article template and its content as featured in the *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) journal

It should be noted that, unlike other art and music journals, the *Türk Müziği (Turkish Music)* journal requires articles to be written in the format of research articles. In this regard, all headings and subheadings found in a scientific research study are included in the article template.

The *Türk Müziği (Turkish Music)* journal expects its authors to submit articles that meet certain quality and standards. This is framed in an article published in the December 2023 issue of the *Türk Müziği (Turkish Music)* journal, which outlines the quality criteria expected in the articles published in the journal. According to this, the following criteria are expected to be included in the published articles:

Table 1. Required features and criteria for music articles (Tortop, 2023)

Criteria	Features and Criteria	Contribution to the article
Criteria 1	Organization, clarity, and precision in abstract writing	Organization
Criteria2	Correct structuring of the introduction section	Organization, fluency, attention-grabbing
Criteria3	Presence of a theoretical foundation in the research	Fundamental construction, reliability
Criteria 4	Presentation of literature related to the research on a global scale	Comprehensiveness, relevance
Criteria 5	Inclusion of economic value and originality in the importance section	Value
Criteria 6	Writing of the aim or problem	Organization, reliability
Criteria 7	Correct selection of the research method	Value, validity
Criteria 8	Explanation of the selection of the sample or documents	Validity
Criteria 9	Explanation of the selection and reasons for data collection tools/documents	Reliability
Criteria 10	Selection and detailed explanation of data analysis	Reliability
Criteria 11	Use of advanced statistics and analysis in the research	Value
Criteria 12	Presentation of findings in alignment with the research aim/problem	Organization
Criteria 13	Sufficient and enriched discussion	Comprehensiveness
Criteria 14	Adequate summarization in the conclusion	Integration, organization
Criteria 15	Recommendations made for practitioners/researchers	Comprehensiveness, usefulness
Criteria 16	Description of the limitations of the research	Comprehensiveness, validity
Criteria17	Inclusion of an acknowledgment section	Detail
Criteria18	Writing of the references according to rules and with meticulous attention	Organization

Considering these criteria, it is believed that the quality of the *Türk Müziği (Turkish Music)* journal will improve as the quality of the articles written according to these standards increases.

TM has published nine issues and 66 articles so far. Of the published articles, 22 were prepared by authors from Azerbaijan and 44 by authors from Türkiye. This indicates that TM has yet to publish articles from other Turkish-speaking states. It is also noted that the editorial board members are exclusively from Azerbaijan and Türkiye.

When analyzing the keywords of the articles published in TM, out of 272 keywords, the most frequently repeated ones are: Music (10), Turkish Music (4), Genre (3), Azerbaijan (3), Turkish Folk Song (3). Twenty-five keywords were repeated twice, while the remaining keywords were mentioned only once. It is observed that almost all of the articles published in TM are research articles, with only two being book reviews.

Regarding its indexing status, TM is indexed in databases such as EBSCO, Index Copernicus, and ISAM. It is noted that the *Türk Müziği (Turkish Music)* journal actively maintains its indexing status, which is emphasized as crucial for enhancing the journal's quality.

Upon reviewing the *Türk Müziği (Turkish Music)* journal's website, it is observed that it offers two services: the Turkish Music Researchers Academy (Web 1) and Support for Young Scientists. These two services aim to improve the article-writing skills of music researchers.

Conclusion

In addition to institutional structures such as conservatories and institutes, academic journals also play a role in advancing Turkish music research in Türkiye. In this study, one of these academic journals, the *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) journal, was examined qualitatively and quantitatively. The research found that TM uses a journal management system and has a technical infrastructure that allows for article submissions through this system. The journal's publication language is exclusively Turkish, and it supports the publication of music research from Turkish-speaking states. The fields in which the journal accepts articles and its objectives are clearly stated. TM shows the details required for quality standards in article submissions through its article template. To date, the *Türk Müziği* (*Turkish Music*) journal has published 66 articles, with Azerbaijan being the country with the second-highest number of published articles after Türkiye. Currently indexed in significant databases, TM offers two free services that are crucial for enhancing its quality, both of which support authors in improving their article-writing skills.

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